

"Application of Taguchi Orthogonal Array Design for the Optimization of Frovatriptan Loaded Transdermal Patches for Migraine Therapy"

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and characterization of transdermal patches for frovatriptan aimed at achieving controlled and sustained drug delivery for effective migraine management. Considering the drug's short half-life and low oral bioavailability due to first pass metabolism, a transdermal approach was selected to enhance therapeutic efficiency. Patches were prepared using the solvent casting method employing HPMC, Ethyl cellulose and Eudragit L100 as film forming polymers, while propylene glycol (PG), ethanol, and DMSO were employed as penetration enhancer. A Taguchi L9 orthogonal design was applied to systematically to optimize formulation variables and identify the most influential factors affecting drug permeation, it was found that the first rank was given to concentration of polymer compare to other factor (type of polymer, concentration of permeation enhancer) and the Ethyl cellulose-based formulation emerged as an optimized patch with the drug permeation of 98.87% after 12hr of diffusion studies and it showed zero order kinetics and fit peppas model, on -fickian (anomalous) diffusion .

Keywords: Frovatriptan, transdermal patches, HPMC, Eudragit RL100 and Ethyl cellulose.

INTRODUCTION

Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS) have become a promising and patient-friendly alternative to traditional oral and parenteral routes, offering controlled and sustained release of drugs through the skin into systemic circulation. They provide several advantages, including avoidance of hepatic first-pass metabolism, improved bioavailability, reduced gastrointestinal irritation, and more consistent plasma drug levels, which together enhance therapeutic efficacy and patient compliance [1,2]. Among TDDS, transdermal patches are preferred for their ability to deliver medications at a predetermined rate, maintain steady-state concentrations, extend dosing intervals, and minimize systemic side effects [3].

Migraine is a long-term and painful neurological condition where patients experience repeated attacks of strong, throbbing headache. These attacks are often accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and sensitivity to light and sound, making daily activities very difficult [4]. Because migraine starts suddenly and affects routine life, patients need treatments that act quickly and effectively.

Frovatriptan is commonly used for treating migraine attacks. It works by acting on 5-HT_{1B/1D} receptors and is preferred because it has a longer half-life and a lower chance of the headache returning compared to many other triptans [5]. But when taken orally, Frovatriptan does not get absorbed well and works slowly because it undergoes extensive first-pass metabolism in the liver, which reduces its bioavailability [6].

Developing a transdermal patch for Frovatriptan offers a strategic solution to overcome these limitations by bypassing hepatic metabolism, initiating faster absorption, and providing steady therapeutic levels over an extended duration. Such a system enhances patient adherence, minimizes dosing frequency, and reduces the risk of fluctuating plasma concentrations associated with oral therapy [7]. Therefore, the formulation of a Frovatriptan transdermal patch holds significant potential to improve migraine treatment outcomes and offer a more efficient, consistent, and patient-centred therapeutic approach.

METHODOLOGY

Analytical method development:

A. UV spectroscopy:

A 100mg of Frovatriptan was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH- 7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution 1 and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). Take 10 ml solution from stock II and volume make up to 100 ml with buffer to get 10 µg/ml. 10 µg/ml solution was scanned from 200-600nm.

B. Construction of calibration curve:

A 100mg of Frovatriptan was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH- 7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution 1 and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). It was further diluted with phosphate buffer pH – 7.4 to get solutions in concentration range of 4 to 16 µg /ml. The absorbances of these solutions were determined spectrophotometrically at 305 nm.

Pre formulation

Compatibility study

A. FTIR study:

The infrared spectrum of the pure Frovatriptan sample was recorded and the spectral analysis was done. The dry sample of drug was directly placed after mixing and triturating with dry potassium bromide.[11]

B. Colour, Odour, Taste and Appearance:

The drug sample was evaluated for its Colour, Odour and Appearance.

C. Melting point determination:

Melting point of the drug sample was determined by capillary method by using melting point apparatus.

d. Determination of solubility:

The solubility of Frovatriptan was determined by adding excess amount of drug in the solvent. The Frovatriptan has very low aqueous solubility. Its solubility is not reported in any official book, so determination of solubility is important. The solubility was determined in

distilled water and phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The procedure can be detailed as follows. Saturated solution of Frovatriptan prepared using 10 ml. of distilled water/ phosphate buffer pH 7.4 in 25 ml volumetric flasks in triplicate. Precaution was taken so that the drug remains in medium in excess. Then by using mechanical shaker, the flasks were shaken for 48 hours. The sample withdrawn (1 ml after filtration) was diluted with appropriate medium and analysed by using UV spectrophotometer at 305 nm and 303 nm for phosphate buffer and distilled water respectively.

Formulation of transdermal patches

Preparation of blank patches:

Polymers of single or in combination were accurately weighed and dissolved in respective solvent and then casted in a Petri-dish with mercury as the plain surface. The films were allowed to dry overnight at room temperature.

Formulation of Drug Incorporated Transdermal Patches:

The matrix-type transdermal patches containing Frovatriptan were prepared using Solvent casting method different concentrations of HPMC ethyl cellulose and Eudragit L 100.[8] The polymers in different concentrations were dissolved in the respective solvents. Then the drug was added slowly in the polymeric solution and stirred on the magnetic stirrer to obtain a uniform solution. Propylene glycol was used as plasticizers. DMSO was used as the penetration enhancer. Then the solution was poured on the Petri dish having surface area of 78 cm² and dried at the room temperature. Then the patches were cut into 2x2 cm² patches. Drug incorporated for each 2x2 cm² patch was 8 mg.

Experimental designs

The Taguchi OA Experimental Design was used to study the effect of different polymer and permeation enhancer at three levels. Three factors (independent variables) such as type of polymer, concentration of penetration enhancer were studied at all the three levels. Drug permeation was taken as the response (dependent variable) as shown in table 1. An L9 orthogonal array was used for choosing the best and optimized formulation. The software used was MINITAB 22 English software [10]

Table 1: Taguchi L⁹ orthogonal array (3³) design of experiment

Independent variable	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Type of polymer	HPMC	Ethyl Cellulose	Eudragit L-100
Conc of Polymer	5	10	15
Conc of Permeation enhancer	0.5	1.0	1.5

Table 2: Taguchi L⁹ orthogonal array (3³) design experimental trials

Trials	Factor A	Factor B	Factor C
1	HPMC	5	0.5
2	HPMC	10	1.0
3	HPMC	15	1.5
4	Ethyl Cellulose	5	0.5
5	Ethyl Cellulose	10	1.5
6	Ethyl Cellulose	15	1.0
7	Eudragit L-100	5	1.5
8	Eudragit L -100	10	0.5
9	Eudragit L – 100	15	1.0

Where,

Factor A: Type of Polymer

Factor B: Conc. Of Polymer

Factor C: Conc. Of Permeation Enhancer (DMSO)

Evaluation Parameters of patches

Physical evaluations

a. Thickness

The thickness of films was measured by digital Vernier callipers with least count 0.001mm. The thickness uniformity was measured at five different sites and average of five readings was taken with standard deviation.

b. Folding endurance

The folding endurance was measured manually for the prepared films. A strip of film (4x3 cm) was cut evenly and repeatedly folded at the same place till it broke. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the exact value of folding endurance.

c. Weight variation

The three disks of 2*1 cm² were cut and weighed on electronic balance for weight variation test. The test was done to check the uniformity of weight and thus check the batch- to- batch variation.

d. Drug content Determination

The prepared drug contained patches specified surface area (2 cm²) were cut and dissolved in (5% of methanol contained) 100ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer, and vigorously Shaked for 12hrs, and then sonicated for 15 minutes, centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 30 min. Filter the drug contained polymeric solution through 42 number Whatman filter paper, then 1ml of the filtrate was taken in a test tube and dilute it for five times with same solvent by using double beam Uv-Visible spectrophotometer to determined drug content at λ_{max} 303 nm. Respected Placebo patch was taken as a blank solution.

Flatness:

A transdermal patch should possess a smooth surface and should not constrict with time. This can be demonstrated with flatness study. For flatness determination, one strip is cut from the center and two from each side of patches. The length of each strip is measured and variation in length is measured by determining percent constriction. Zero percent constriction is equivalent to 100 percent flatness.

$$\% \text{ constriction} = I_1 - I_2 \times 100$$

l_2 = Final length of each strip

l_1 = Initial length of each strip

***In-vitro* Drug Diffusion Study:**

The *in vitro* study of drug permeation through the semi permeable membrane was performed using a Franz type glass diffusion cell. The modified cell having higher capacity (25 ml) is used to maintain sink condition. This membrane was mounted between the donor and receptor compartment of a diffusion cell. The transdermal patch was placed on the membrane and covered with aluminium foil. The receptor compartment of the diffusion cell was filled with isotonic phosphate buffer of pH 7.4. The hydrodynamics in the receptor compartment were maintained by stirring with a magnetic bead at constant rpm and the temperature was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The diffusion was carried out for 12 h and 1 ml sample was withdrawn at an interval of 1 h. The receptor phase was replenished with an equal volume of phosphate buffer at each sample withdrawal. The samples were analysed for drug content spectrophotometrically at 305 nm

Drug release kinetics:

Diffusion data of above two methods was fitted in Zero order, First order and Higuchi equations. The mechanism of drug release was determined by using Higuchi equation.

Zero-Order Kinetics:

Zero order as cumulative amount of Percentage drug released vs time

$$C = K_0 t$$

Where K_0 is the zero-order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t is the time in hours. A graph of concentration vs time would yield a straight line with a slope equal to K_0 and intercept the origin of the axes.

First order kinetics:

First order as log cumulative percentage of log (%) cumulative drug remaining vs time,

$$\log C = \log C_0 - k t / 2.303$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of drug, k is the first order constant, and t is the time.

Higuchi Model:

Higuchi's model as cumulative percentage of drug released vs square root of time

$$Q = K t^{1/2}$$

Where K is the constant reflecting the design variables of the system and t is the time in hours. Hence, drug release rate is proportional to the reciprocal of the square root of time.

Kors Meyer Peppas equations:

Korsmeyer peppas equation used to determine the mechanism of drug release from the polymer matrix of the tablet. Log cumulative percentage of drug released VS Log time, and the exponent n was calculated through the slope of the straight line.

$$M_t/M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where M_t/M_∞ is the fractional solute release, t is the release time, K is a kinetic constant characteristic of the drug/polymer system, and n is an exponent that characterizes the mechanism of release of tracers. For cylindrical matrix tablets, if the exponent $n = 0.45$, then the drug release mechanism is Fickian diffusion, and if $0.45 < n < 0.89$, then it is non-Fickian or anomalous diffusion. An exponent value of 0.89 is indicative of Case-II Transport or typical zero-order release.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially the drug was tested by UV to know their significant absorption maximum which can be used for the diffusion study of the drug.

Analysis of drug:

A. UV spectroscopy:

The lambda max of Frovatriptan was found to be 305 nm.

B. Construction of calibration curve:

Figure 1: Standard Calibration Curve of Frovatriptan

Pre formulation study,

Nine formulation trials were done with the aim to achieve the successful matrix type Frovatriptan transdermal patches.

A. Colour, Odour, taste and appearance

Table 3: Results of identification tests of drug no table

Parameter	Frovatriptan
Color	White
Odor	Odorless
Taste	Bitter
Appearance	A white powder

B. Melting point determination:

The melting point of Drug (Frovatriptan) was found to be 172-174 °C.

C. Determination of solubility:

The solubility of drug in distilled water was found to be 0.0177

Evaluation of Patch

The formulations F1 to F9 were varying in thickness when compared to other formulations which is due to the variation in the polymer concentration. Which shows the increase in polymer concentration increases the thickness of patch. For all other formulations it was found to be in between 0.051±0.006 to 0.059±0.001mm. All formulations from F1 to F9 Shows weight variation in between 116±2.60 to 120±6.14mg.

Folding endurance from formulations F1 to F9 was found to be in between 70 ± 5.16 to 79 ± 2.53 which can withstand the folding of the skin.

All formulations showed % drug content in the range of 95.26 ±2.10 to 99.43 ±9.99.

Table 4: Evaluation of patches

Formulation Code	Average weight(mg)	Thickness (mm)	Folding endurance	Flatness (%)	Flatness	% Drug Content
F1	120±5.93	0.056±0.004	70 ± 5.16	96	Transparent	95.26 ±2.10
F2	119±1.64	0.052±0.002	76 ± 1.52	98	Transparent	98.90 ±0.36
F3	118±0.13	0.059±0.001	72 ± 6.90	98	Transparent	97.83 ±6.29
F4	116±2.60	0.051±0.006	78 ± 0.16	94	Transparent	96.16 ±9.15
F5	119±1.89	0.053±0.004	75 ± 5.72	96	Transparent	98.97 ±4.48
F6	120±6.14	0.055±0.003	79 ± 2.53	96	Transparent	99.43 ±9.99
F7	117±2.79	0.056±0.004	76 ± 7.10	94	Transparent	98.82 ±3.15
F8	119±1.36	0.057±0.001	70 ± 9.98	97	Transparent	98.97 ±2.27
F9	118±0.42	0.054±0.004	71 ± 4.43	97	Transparent	97.34 ±7.60

***In vitro* diffusion study:**

All the formulations were evaluated for *in vitro* diffusion study using Franz type diffusion cell under specific condition such as temp maintained at 32 ± 0.5 °C. The diffusion was carried out for 12 h and 5 ml sample was withdrawn at an interval of 1 hrs.

Figure: 2 Cumulative % drug permeation of Frovatriptan patch (F1, F2, F3)

Formulations F1 to F3 (prepared using different concentrations of HPMC 5, 10, 15mg), it was found that the drug release from the patch depend on the concentration of polymer. As the polymer concentration increases the drug release also increases.

Figure: 3 Cumulative % drug permeation of Frovatriptan patch (F4, F5, F6)

The formulation (F4) containing 5mg concentration of polymer showed maximum drug released of 98.14 % after 8 hours. The formulation (F5) containing 10mg concentration polymer showed maximum drug release of 97.91 after 10 hours. But formulation (F6) showed the drug release for desired and longest time period (12hrs) when compared to F4 and F5. Thus this marks as an evidence that concentration of polymer has synergic affect on drug release.

Figure: 4 Cumulative % drug permeation of Frovatriptan patch (F7, F8, F9)

The formulations F7 to F9 were prepared using different concentrations of Eudragit L (5, 10, 15mg) the drug release from the patch is dependent on the concentration of polymer. The formulation F7 showed maximum drug release of 96.65% after 9 hours. The formulation F8 showed maximum drug released of 98.97 % at 11th hr. The F9 formulation showed less drug release of 95.36% at 12 hr.

Among all 9 formulations F6 formulation showed sustained drug release from the patch. F6 formulation passed all evaluation parameters.

Kinetic models for Frovatriptan

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyse the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

The optimized formulation followed peppas release kinetics and fit peppas model, on -fickian (anomalous) diffusion.

Table: 5 Kinetics data of F6 Frovatriptan patch

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG (%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining
0	0	0			2.000				100
22.92	1	1.000	1.360	0.000	1.887	22.920	0.0436	-0.640	77.08
30.36	2	1.414	1.482	0.301	1.843	15.180	0.0329	-0.518	69.64
37.61	3	1.732	1.575	0.477	1.795	12.537	0.0266	-0.425	62.39
44.53	4	2.000	1.649	0.602	1.744	11.133	0.0225	-0.351	55.47
51.88	5	2.236	1.715	0.699	1.682	10.376	0.0193	-0.285	48.12
64.46	6	2.449	1.809	0.778	1.551	10.743	0.0155	-0.191	35.54

71.87	7	2.646	1.857	0.845	1.449	10.267	0.0139	-0.143	28.13
79.29	8	2.828	1.899	0.903	1.316	9.911	0.0126	-0.101	20.71
86.14	9	3.000	1.935	0.954	1.142	9.571	0.0116	-0.065	13.86
92.49	10	3.162	1.966	1.000	0.876	9.249	0.0108	-0.034	7.51
96.73	11	3.317	1.986	1.041	0.515	8.794	0.0103	-0.014	3.27
98.87	12	3.464	1.995	1.079	0.053	8.239	0.0101	-0.005	1.13

COMPATIBILITY STUDIES:

IR SPECTROSCOPY:

The compatibility studies of the drug with excipients indicate no characteristic visual changes and no additional peaks were observed during FT-IR studies as depicted in the Figure 5 & 6.

Figure 5.: FTIR Spectrum of pure Frovatriptan drug

Figure 6: FTIR of Optimized formulation

DISCUSSION

The optimized formulation, prepared using ethyl cellulose (EC) as the matrix polymer along with a synergistic combination of propylene glycol (PG), ethanol, and DMSO, exhibited the highest permeation among all formulations. This enhancement can be attributed to the combined effects of the polymeric matrix and the selected permeation enhancers. Ethyl cellulose, being a hydrophobic, semi-permeable polymer, forms a dense matrix with controlled diffusional pathways that modulate drug release while maintaining patch integrity [12–14]. At optimal concentration, EC provides a balance between mechanical strength and permeability, enabling sustained and controlled release of frovatriptan through the transdermal route.

Propylene glycol significantly contributed to enhanced permeation by acting both as a co-solvent and humectant. PG is known to increase drug solubility within the polymeric film, hydrate the stratum corneum, and fluidize intercellular lipids, resulting in reduced diffusional resistance [15–17]. Its ability to occupy hydrogen-bonding sites in keratin and enhance drug

partitioning into the SC further contributes to improved flux [15-17]. Moreover, PG has been reported to increase thermodynamic activity of the drug in the formulation, thus enhancing its driving force for skin permeation [20].

Ethanol also played a crucial role by extracting stratum corneum lipids, disrupting lipid packing, and altering the barrier structure of the skin. This results in transient fluidization of the SC and enhanced permeability [18–19]. Ethanol's volatility also leads to supersaturation of the drug on the skin surface, which increases the permeation gradient and accelerates drug diffusion [19]. Studies have reported that ethanol and PG act synergistically to enhance permeation more effectively than when used independently [20-24].

DMSO, one of the most potent chemical permeation enhancers, enhanced permeation in F6 by penetrating rapidly into deeper skin layers and altering both keratin and lipid domains [21–22]. DMSO disrupts protein conformations, increases SC hydration, and creates micro-channels within the lipid matrix, resulting in significant reduction in barrier resistance [21–23]. Its strong ability to reorganize ceramide bilayers and induce a more permeable liquid-crystalline phase further explains its high enhancer efficiency [22–23].

Figure 7: Main Effects Plot for Means

The ranks obtained for each factor will determine its effect on the response (drug permeation) From Figure 7. It can be inferred that Factor B i.e. Conc of polymer has a great influence on

the response. The other 2 Factor A & C i.e., Type of polymer, Conc of permeation enhancer has equal influence on the response. Therefore, the order of independent variables on which drug permeation depends was concentration of polymer > type of polymer, concentration of Permeation Enhancer.

CONCLUSION

The present study showed that optimized formulation F6 containing ethyl cellulose as the primary polymer and PG, Ethanol, DMSO as a permeation enhancer. The optimized formulation demonstrated superior, drug permeability, uniformity, mechanical strength, and sustained release compared to other polymer combinations. The result confirms that transdermal delivery can overcome Frovatriptan's oral limitations such as low bioavailability and first pass metabolism, offering a promising alternative for effective migraine management.

REFERENCES

1. **Priessnitz MR, Langer R.** Transdermal drug delivery. *Nature Biotechnology*. 2008.
2. **Alexander A, et al.** Recent innovations in transdermal drug delivery system. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2012.
3. **Guy RH.** Current status and future prospects of transdermal drug delivery. *Pharm Res*. 2010.
4. **Goadsby PJ, et al.** Pathophysiology of migraine. *Physiol Rev*. 2017.
5. **Ferrari MD, et al.** Triptans and their use in migraine. *N Engl J Med*. 2001.
6. **Tfelt-Hansen P, et al.** Pharmacokinetics of triptans. *Clin Pharmacokinet*. 2000.
7. **Jain A, et al.** Transdermal drug delivery approaches and advancements. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm*. 2020.
8. **Prajapati ST, Patel CG, Patel CN.** Formulation and evaluation of transdermal patch of Repaglinide. *ISRN Pharm*. 2011; 2011:651909. doi:10.5402/2011/651909.
9. **Głąb M, Drabczyk A, Kudlacik-Kramarczyk S, Duarte Guigou M, Makara A, Gajda P, Jampilek J, Tyliszczak B.** Starch solutions prepared under different conditions as modifiers of chitosan/poly (aspartic acid)-based hydrogels. *Materials*. 2021;14(16):4443. doi:10.3390/ma14164443.
10. **Ruhi Anjum , Lakshmi PK.** Dolutegravir sodium loaded solid lipid nanoparticles: a vaginal drug delivery system for pre-exposure prophylaxis of HIV. *J Res Pharm*. 2020;24(4):552–561. doi:10.35333/jrp.2020.203.
11. **Sabir F, Qindeel M, Rehman AU, Ahmad NM, Khan GM, Csoka I, Ahmed N.** Curcumin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles patch for transdermal delivery: development and optimisation. *J Microencapsul*. 2021; 38:233–248. doi:10.1080/02652048.2021.1899321.
12. **Ghosal R, Chakraborty S, Pradhan M.** Development, evaluation and optimization of transdermal patches of Frovatriptan. *J Pharm Sci*. 2014;103(2):424–432.
13. **Akhtar N, et al.** Formulation and characterization of polymeric films for transdermal drug delivery. *Adv Polym Technol*. 2018;37(8):2975–2983.
14. **Khanna R, et al.** Influence of polymers on drug release from transdermal patches. *Int J Pharm*. 2010;392(1–2):45–54.
15. **Lane ME.** Skin penetration enhancers. *J Control Release*. 2006;103(2):412–418.

16. **Williams AC, Barry BW.** Penetration enhancers. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2003;55(10):1157–1172.
17. **Barry BW.** Mode of action of penetration enhancers in human skin. *Pharm Res.* 1987;4(3):193–205.
18. **Aungst BJ.** Skin penetration enhancers and their mechanisms. *Pharm Res.* 1989;6(8):597–603.
19. **Cornwell PA, et al.** Mechanisms of action of alcohol-based penetration enhancers. *Drug Dev Ind Pharm.* 1994;20(2):245–256.
20. **El-Maghraby GM, et al.** Effect of ethanol and propylene glycol on skin permeation of drugs. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2008;69(3):1150–1156.
21. **Stoughton RB.** Dimethyl sulfoxide and skin permeation. *Arch Dermatol.* 1965;91(6):657–664.
22. **Williams AC, et al.** Mechanisms of DMSO-enhanced skin penetration. *Skin Pharmacol Physiol.* 2004;17(3):141–149.
23. **Karande P, Jain A, Mitragotri S.** Discovery of transdermal penetration enhancers using synchrotron studies. *PNAS.* 2005;102(13):4688–4693.
24. **Walters KA, et al.** Enhancement of transdermal drug delivery by alcohol and glycol systems. *Int J Pharm.* 2002;231(1):1–12.
25. **Reddy BP, et al.** Evaluation of polymeric films containing penetration enhancers for transdermal delivery. *AAPS PharmSciTech.* 2015;16(2):339–350.
26. **Kalia YN, et al.** Principles of skin permeation and enhancer technologies. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2001;46(1–3):1–26.